

4 EU demo cases

1 replication demo in South Africa

10 mines around Europe

10 different raw materials including 4 CRMs

European Mining in the Green and Digital Era

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Use Cases

MASTERMINE is the go-to ecosystem for mines that envision digitalisation, environmental sustainability, productivity monitoring and public acceptance within their strategic goals. It is based on an Industrial Metaverse approach to build a digitalized copy of a real-world mine.

TERNA MAG MINES
Greece

THARSIS MINES
Spain

TAPOJARVI MINES
Finland

SIBANYE-STILLWATER MINE
South Africa

JSW MINES
Poland